

Mission Science Data Systems

(A Mission-Specific Template)

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Intended Usage

This document template is a community effort to publish Science Data Systems (SDS) existing in industry and the decisions, technologies, and people that pioneer this landscape. We encourage you and your team, regardless of which Science Mission Directorate (SMD) mission area you represent, to use this as a standardized guide to “tell your story” so that the community may benefit and future missions might learn and utilize these technological advances rather than introducing further redundancy.

In 2024 and 2025, three community workshops brought together participants from a range of institutions, mission areas, and system/data scales used in scientific research. These efforts reflect a shared commitment to developing common frameworks, interfaces, and architecture from the diverse systems already used. An introductory report within this special edition will highlight these workshops and summarize key findings.

The intended audience of these submissions are fellow designers and developers of SDS.

Note: From this point forward, the term SDS will be used instead of other analogous entities (e.g., Science Operations Center (SOC)).

Abstract

Provide the desire for including your mission's SDS in this collection and the needs of mission systems to be considered collectively rather than individually.

Brief summary of the paper / high-level points should be included (no cliffhangers)--someone reading abstract / intro / conclusion should have a good idea of the paper.

1 Introduction

1.1 SDS Overview

1.1.1 Background

- Relevant heritage (and missions)
- What the audience needs to know to understand the SDS

1.1.2 Current State/Status of SDS

- Mission phase and state of the system (is it under development, currently operating, undergoing modernization efforts, etc.)

1.1.3 Community and Audience

- What is the community that uses/benefits from the SDS?
- Who would especially benefit from reading this paper?

1.2 Mission Objectives

1.2.1 Summary

- Human-readable plain language summary of the mission, high level scientific and non-scientific objectives

1.2.2 Mission References

- Table is optional
- Cite mission paper
- Cite other relevant publicly-available items (e.g., OSDMP, DMP)
- Other examples: “first light” paper or mission-defining science results; repository for the SDS if developed in the open (even better, concept DOI); etc.

1.3 Instrumentation

1.3.1 Mission Observables

1.3.2 Quantities Measured

- Table of quantities measured
- High Level

- Reference Section 2 detailed descriptions

1.3.3 Measurement Techniques

1.3.4 Instrumentation References

- Cite instrument papers

1.4 SDS in Mission Context

Potential topics to cover: (non-exhaustive)

- PI-lead or otherwise?
- SDS unified for the mission or multiple (instrument, suite, etc.)?
- Division of labor between SDS, instrument teams, mission facilities for writing code, validation of products, etc.
- Relationship with MOC
- Funding source(s)?
- Size/class of mission
- Where the SDS "sits" in the ground segment (maybe a high level ground systems data flow diagram)
- Heritage / history of the relevant research / instrument team
- How early were RSE's involved in the mission planning / conception process?

2 Mission Needs

2.1 Introduction / Summary

High level summary of requirements/desirements (what you got going into it)

Can also include a table of key driving requirements

2.2 Programmatic Constraints

Restrictions on launch date, cost caps, decision to have system complete before launch, etc.

Export controlled information and need to partition any other sensitive / proprietary information

2.2.1 Ground Systems

- Operations
 - Payload Operation Center (POC)
 - Science Operation Center (SOC)

- Data Retrieval
- Scientific Planning, Commanding, and Optimization
- Multiple streams of data, e.g. operational SWx stream

2.2.2 Data Volumes and Scalability

- Data Volumes
- Rates and Latencies
 - *Latency between acquisition and downlink, and between downlink and delivery...*
 - Burst / survey, SITL, etc
- Cost Considerations
- Scalability

2.3 Archive requirements

What archive to deliver to, what requirements do they levy on file formats and such?

2.4 Open Science Requirements

Reference any requirements for open science (e.g. SPD-41a or similar policies) that apply to your mission or SDS. Institutional restrictions, encouragement, and/or processes (tech transfer) for release of data and software; additional funding or projects supporting open science.

3 *Science Data System Design*

Include discussion of how design addresses mission needs from section 2

Include relevant trade studies.

Discuss as-built design. Summarize relevant changes from initial design to as-built, to be referenced in lessons learned.

3.1 Architecture Overview

Architecture diagram(s), internal and external interfaces

3.2 Data Products

3.2.1 Scientific Deliverables

- Collections
- Data Level definitions
 - Level, definition from the DAAC, the way you interpreted the definition, and any ways you were not able to make that definition work for your scenario

3.2.2 Data product design philosophy

- Easy to reuse for derived products, v independently usable w/o additional work?
- How many products?
- What goes in what products?
- Feed this into lessons learned, how did these decisions work out?

3.2.3 Archive

- Which products did you decide to archive?
- Were there any specific data needs for archival? (any specific metadata needed, any label files needed, etc.)
- How we generate the data/metadata files and interact with the archive (requirements are covered above)
- Link to the data holdings

3.3 Computing Infrastructure

3.3.1 Hosting Strategy

- Cloud, on-prem, or hybrid

3.3.2 Information Technology

- IT Support
- Security (DMZ, public access)

3.3.3 Operating Authority

ATOs or similar required?

3.3.4 Disaster Recovery and Continuity of Operations

3.4 Components

Note whether the components are open-source, proprietary, reused, etc.

3.5 Data Flow

Note whether the tools are open-source, proprietary, reused, etc.

Note any difference in data streams, e.g. a near-time space weather product v. standard

3.5.1 Telemetry

- Volume
- Dimensionality
- Rate(s) and frequency of downlink
- Format (CCSDS format or not, compression, etc.)

3.5.2 Ingest

- Data Transfers
- Downlink: how data gets to the mission team/operations

3.5.3 Processing Pipelines and Controls

- Automation
 - Triggers
 - Dependency management
 - Reprocessing
 - Semantic Versioning
 - Structure (including ancillary files)
- How data gets to the end user
 - Interfaces/Gateways
 - Open Science (SPD-41A)
 - FAIR principles
- Out-of-loop processing
 - Anomaly Investigation
 - Refinement and debugging

3.5.4 Science Processing Codes

Brief summary and any points of interest for the data production codes

(e.g. L1 -> L2)

3.5.5 Data Management

- Versioning
- Storage
- Inventory/Catalog/Databases
- Metadata

3.5.6 Archive

- Interfaces / APIs (infrastructure to deliver)
- Naming conventions

3.6 Instrument Monitoring and Trending

- Tools and processes for monitoring the instrument(s) and responding to anomalies
- Alarms and notification approach/management

3.7 Development

3.7.1 Development Team

- Experience levels of team
- Team makeup/background and staffing levels

3.7.2 Team Management

- Mentorship, training, engagement

3.7.3 Project Management

- Agile, waterfall, hybrid
- Best Practices Paper; NPR 7150.2
- Source code management processes

3.7.4 Testing Approach

- Philosophy around TDD, unit testing, integration testing, etc.
- Verification testing
- Mission simulations/data rehearsals

4 Documentation and Support

4.1 Software

4.1.1 Software Documentation

- May include analysis utilities as well

4.1.2 SDS Operator Documentation

- Executable documentation (includes analysis too)
- How to run the system/system components/pipeline

4.2 Mission Science and User Documentation

- Data product user guides
- Data product specifications
- ATBD (Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document)/CMAD (Calibration Methods and Algorithms Document)

4.3 SDS Support

- Support for the community, archive, instrument team
- On-call support

5 Mission Data and Software Usage Policies OR Open Science

- If you have open science, use “Open Science”, if hybrid, use “Open Science” and explain ways you’re pushing towards open science, if not use “Mission Data and Software Usage” as the section title
- **Note:** There will be a consolidated paper of this special issue that encapsulates the “best practices” from each of the submitted SDS mission-specific issues.

5.1 Rules and Guidelines

- Rules of the road
- Data and software licensing and what led to that choice
- Open science policies levied on users and how you get them to do it

5.2 Mission Practices

The [Open Science for Missions and Observatories paper](#) provides a wealth of open science practices that can be incorporated into missions in the pre-proposal, pre-launch, and post-launch phases . These practices are not limited to the typical practices associated with artifacts, e.g. creating a DOI for generated software, but also includes culture practices. Some of these practices may have been implemented even if not named “open science”. We are interested to know:

What open science practices, whether listed in the paper or not, did the mission choose to incorporate?

What benefits or problems did the mission experience due to incorporating each practice?

If you could go back in time, what would you choose differently concerning incorporating Open Science practices?

What suggestions concerning open science practices do you offer for other missions based on your experience?

Were there any barriers to implementing these practices and if/how were they overcome? (this may also get captured in Lessons Learned)

6 Sustainment and Modernization

6.1 Development and Maintenance Progression

- Diagram or table including key dates, showing the progression of development. Include key changes in operations including disaster recovery events, major changes to operational approach, upgrades to the system, evolution of open science approach, etc.
 - Example of types of things to include:
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11214-022-00919-x>

6.2 Operations

Day-to-day operations of the SDS in practice.

6.3 Migrations, updates, and technical debt

Updates to the system architecture or implementation based on changing needs or environment. Obsolescence management. Migration to new hardware as reach warranty or lifespan. Changing dependencies. Disaster recovery / redeployment if it has happened (or drills as relevant)

7 Lessons Learned

What qualifies as a lesson learned?

Err on the side of inclusion and bravely share both positive and negative experiences. For widespread lessons learned, reviewers may ask to cut an item in your paper in favor of including it in the best practices paper at the end of the special issue.

Loose definition: Things you wish you had known going in or would like others to know that are based on your experience in this project. For example, risky decisions that paid off, things that bit you, something that wasn't guaranteed to work but did.

Consider lessons learned in areas of project organization and management, infrastructure, system components and architecture, data flow, data product design, metadata contents and approach, archive strategy, software reuse, interfacing between teams and components, institutional support, collaboration, user interaction/support, proposal involvement, requirements testing approach

Category	Impact Positive(+), Negative(-), Informational(I)	Description	Project Phase	Section
<i>Data flow, system components</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>Used great tool for decom</i>	<i>Ongoing</i>	<i>7.1</i>
<i>Organization</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>Not enough support</i>	<i>Planning</i>	<i>N/A</i>

7.1 Example: Used Great Tool for Decom

Discuss the lesson including any context for making the decisions around what led to this lesson, why the lesson had the impact it did, any mitigations (if applicable), whether the mitigations worked (if applicable), whether the issue/benefits still going

8 Conclusion

Can be very short, what is most important for the reader to know? (If someone from HQ is skimming these papers, what should they know?). Do not repeat the abstract (which should be where the summary is)

- Any most important elements, design decisions, or lessons learned you particularly want to highlight*
- Key or unique drivers of mission development*
- Anything that makes this mission unique*
- Any future directions to take*

Acronyms / Glossary

References

- Citations to all software (GitHUB/Zenodo DOIs with specific versions)
- OSDMPs/DMPs
- Related instrument/mission papers